

International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC)

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<http://airccse.org/journal/mvsc/ijmvsc.html>

Scope & Topics

The International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC) is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles that contribute new results in all areas of value and supply chain management. The journal provides a platform to disseminate new ideas and new research, advance theories, and propagate best practices in the management of value and supply chain management, looking across both product and service-based businesses. This will include works based in service management, logistics and distribution, operations management, process management, flow control, and customer service. The journal offers a forum in which academics, consultants, and practitioners in a variety of fields can exchange ideas to further research and improve practices in all areas of business. The International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC) seek to establish new collaborations, new best practices, and new theories in the management of both product and service-based organizations around the world.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of value and supply chain management.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Supply chain management
- Value chain management
- Analytical frameworks
- Business-to-business marketing
- Change management
- Channel management
- Cultural issues
- Customer service
- Customer retention strategies
- Demand forecasting and planning
- Distribution channels
- Economic issues
- Information technology in product distribution
- Information technology in service delivery
- Knowledge management
- Legal and regulatory issues
- Logistics management and planning (inbound, outbound and reverse logistics)
- Manufacturing methods and strategies
- Metrics and Measurement
- Network design and routing
- Quality control and improvement
- Performance metrics
- Purchasing and procurement
- e-procurement and e-commerce
- Product innovation and development

- Sourcing strategies
- Supplier selection
- Vendor management and selection

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail:jjmvsc@airccse.org . Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates:

- **Submission Deadline : August 11, 2018**
- Notification : September 11, 2018
- Final Manuscript Due : September 18, 2018
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief